

Analysis of Marketing Vs Online Marketing

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Abstract

It process of the Product should be reach ultimate consumer nothing but marketing. We use a large variety of goods and services in our daily life. We know that the businessman produces goods and services for our use. These are not necessarily produced at the places where they are consumed or used. While the obvious purpose of internet marketing is to sell goods, services or advertising over the internet, it's not the only purpose a business using internet marketing may have a company may be marketing online to communicate a message about itself brand or to conduct research.

Introduction

Market is a place .Marketing is dealing between a Buyer and a Seller. We use a large variety of goods and services in our daily life. We know that the businessman or manufacturer produces goods and services for our routine use. These are not necessarily produced at the places where they are consumed or used. Even in villages, now-a-days you find the products manufactured all over India and in other countries. This implies that the manufacturers must be making efforts to ensure that their products are in demand and reach the ultimate consumers all over the globe. So, when you go to the market to buy a readymade shirt you find that there are several options available to you in terms of quality of cloth used, design, colour, price etc. Internet marketing means different things to different people. While the obvious purpose of internet marketing is to sell goods, services or advertising over the internet, it's not only purpose of a business but also using internet marketing may have a company, it may be marketing online to communicate a message about brand itself or to conduct research.

Objectives

- Advantages and Disadvantages of Marketing
- Advantages and Disadvantages of Online Marketing
- Analysis For Marketing VS Online Marketing
- The possible to Marketing &Online marketing the world
- Conclusion
- Reference

Benefit of Marketing

- The Marketing used to Buyer and Consumer Face to Face Communication Directly.
- The very quick (or) fastest to Marketing.
- The price change for Product.
- An obvious advantage of marketing is the promotion of your business; getting the recognition and attention of your target audience across a wide ranging or specific market.
- Going hand-in-hand with this is the enhanced brand recognition. Over time potential customers and members of the public will begin to associate your logo and your brand with your business.
- Every business needs to ‘spend money to make money’. Investing in marketing is no different. The most important advantage of marketing is therefore quite simply improving the businesses profits by boosting sales.

Limitation of Marketing

- The time is not saved.
- The first disadvantage of marketing in general is the cost. Advertising and marketing costs money. If you don't do the proper research then you might end up throwing money away. Wasting marketing efforts by targeting the wrong audience using an inappropriate medium would be a serious and costly mistake. So it is important to do your research beforehand and keep your costs to a minimum.
- As well as the financial cost, marketing your business will require investment of time. Researching the appropriate marketing strategy, designing and writing the adverts, getting them published, dealing with any response. It's important to spend time keeping track of how successful or not your marketing campaign is. A potential disadvantage of marketing here is the risk of time wasted for an unsuccessful campaign.
- Research shows that people in general have to see a piece of information between 3 and 30 times before it sinks in. So the obvious disadvantage of marketing here is the fact that your marketing campaign will need to be ongoing and consistent. Increasing costs and time spent on it. This is where drip marketing comes in.

Advantages of Online Marketing

1. Lower Cost

Compared to traditional or offline marketing, it is far cheaper to promote your business and other money making ventures online. This is especially true about advertising. In fact, some of the techniques for promoting a business or making money online are completely FREE. Unlike traditional ad media such as the TV and newspapers, you will only spend a split fraction of what it will cost to promote a business traditionally. In addition to being cost-effective, internet marketing is also time-saving as it takes less time to find customers and accomplish transactions.

The returns on investment that comes with online marketing exceed that of conventional marketing. When you implement the online promotional techniques correctly, you will get higher and instant returns on the money you spend to place an ad online. And as mentioned earlier, most techniques are completely free and will yield good returns.

2. Global Audience

There's also the advantage of gaining a global audience (unlike a traditional business that is restricted within its boundaries of operation) with your online business. This opens up tons of new opportunities and prepares you to compete on a global scale. So, even if your offline office is closed for business, customers and prospects will still find you through your website and place their orders.

3. Reliable Technology

The reliable technology that powers the web, hence your internet-based business is one of the major benefits of hosting your business online. And, the technologies are getting better and more sophisticated by the day. So, with the top-notch technologies online, you don't have to worry about your emails being delivered (email marketing) to your target audience on a timely manner – delivery is almost instant! On the other hand, the traditional mailing system takes days, or even weeks to deliver mail to their destinations.

Disadvantages of Internet Marketing

1. Face-to-Face Contact is Limited

Limited face to face contact is one of the major drawbacks of internet marketing. Businesses that are carried out solely online do not usually get to build strong personal rapport with their customers. As a result, they may eventually lose some of their customers to their traditional competitors who engage strong customer service tactics.

2. Marketing Complexity

The virtual nature of internet marketing increases marketing complexity. New entrants tend to be confused on how to choose profitable online marketing techniques. Customers also face complexities in the aspects of shopping online. In fact, the un-informed consumers would rather stick to conventional buying than endure such online purchase complexities.

Analysis for Marketing Vs Online Marketing

- Marketing is used to Village people. But Online Marketing used to City people.
- Marketing is Money Saved. But it is not possible.
- Not time saved to Marketing. But Time saved Online Marketing

The analysis to 1000 people research analysis follows.

Male = 600

Female = 400

Age	15-25	26-35	36-45
Male	300	200	100
Female	150	100	150

How do you like people Marketing and Online Marketing

- Marketing used to people in 300 people
- Online Marketing used to people in 700 people
- The people mostly selected in Online Marketing

How do you the world possible to Marketing and Online Marketing

- The World Possible to Marketing in Year 2017 40% people using.
- The Marketing in Year 2018 20% people used.
- The Online Marketing in Year 2017 60% people used.
- The Online Marketing in Year 2018 80% people used.
- The world people mostly selected in Online Marketing.

The Importance of marketing

Marketing is important to the business, consumer as well as the society. This is evident from the following.

- (d) As of October 2018 almost 4.2 billion people were active internet users and 3.4 billion were social media users. China, India and the United States rank ahead all other countries in terms of internet users. This gives a marketer an unprecedented number of customers to reach with product and service offerings, available 24 hours a day, seven days a week. The interactive nature of the internet facilitates immediate communication between businesses and consumers, allowing businesses to respond quickly to the needs of consumers and changes in the marketplace. “Everyone has the internet in their pocket all the time, and this changes everything for small businesses”. Online reviews have become one of the most important components in purchasing decisions by consumers in North America. According to a survey conducted by Dimensional Research which included over 1000 participants, 90% of respondents said that positive online reviews influenced their buying decisions and 94% will use a business with at least four stars. Interestingly, negative reviews typically came from online review sites whereas Face book was the main source of positive reviews. Forrester Research predicts that by 2020, 42% of in-store sales will be from customers who are influenced by web product research. Online reviews, then, have become another form of internet marketing that small businesses can’t afford to ignore. While many small businesses think that they can’t do anything about online reviews, that’s not true. Just by actively encouraging customers to post reviews about their experience small businesses can weight online reviews positively. Sixty-eight percent of consumers left a local business review when asked. So assuming a business’s products or services are not subpar, unfair negative reviews will get buried by reviews by happier customers.

Conclusion

The marketer, irrespective of operation in an urban or a rural area, gives importance to marketing, its concept and objective of satisfying consumers with goods and services for a profit. The four P’s which make up marketing mix are equally relevant in both the cases. However the basic difference in

these, two segments lie in demographic, socio cultural and economic environment. As generations evolve and technology develops, the advancement in the field of marketing and advertisements has been immense. No longer are businesses bound by the limitations of traditional marketing techniques. The old has been heavily replaced by the new. One of the newest and most effective strategies has been of online marketing, which is the topic that this whole e-book was centered on. Online marketing utilizes the internet and its wealth of resources for promotional, profile-raising purposes. After covering some types of online marketing, which included email marketing and social media marketing, we reviewed some of the common trends and shifts that resulted from this advancement.

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